

Science

DOES THE HEALTH CARE PROVIDER FULFILL THE NEEDS AND EXPECTATIONS OF WOMEN DURING INTRA-PARTUM AND IMMEDIATE POSTPARTUM PERIOD IN A SELECTED GOVT. HOSPITAL OF WEST BENGAL?

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Abstract

A descriptive study was conducted to assess the needs and expectations and fulfilment of needs and expectations of intra-partum and immediate post partum women. The findings revealed that in the area of esteem need all women (100%) wanted respectful maternity care. Intra-partum women had different types of need i.e. physiological need (92%) personal and psychological need (90%) social needs (98.61%) and safety needs (95%). Among various types of intra partum need 61.54% physiological needs were totally fulfilled. Pain relieving needs of immediate postpartum women were totally fulfilled (100%). Statistically significant association were found between educational status and fulfilment of personal & psychological need ($\chi^2 = 5.257$) and gravida and fulfilment of informational needs ($\chi^2 = 14.920$) at df 1, $p < 0.05$ level of significance. There was a moderate negative correlation ($r = -0.548$) found between gravid and intra partum and immediate postpartum needs. There was a significant mean difference ($t = 5.399$, at df 118) between fulfilment of needs of primigravida and multigravida women at 0.05 level of significance. The study has an implication in nursing service by assessing the needs & expectations of intra partum and immediate postpartum women, the total needs can be fulfilled by health care provider.

Keywords: Needs; Expectations; Fulfilment; Health Care Provider.

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1. Introduction

Normal labour is a spontaneous process of expulsion of the foetus and placenta. However, it is important to remember that the intra-partum and immediate postpartum women have some different kind of needs. Health care provider has the responsibility to assess the needs and provide

care to women according to their needs. The first 48 hours after delivery are the most critical in the entire post-partum period. During this time they are not able to take care of self. They are suffering from pain at abdomen, episiotomy suturing. They are hungry, tired and fatigued. They are not able to take care of newborn baby also.

1.1. Background of the Study

Pregnancy and birth are unique processes for women. Women hold different needs and expectations during child bearing based on their knowledge, experiences, and belief systems, cultural, social and family backgrounds. These differences should be understood and respected, and care is adapted and organized to meet the individual needs of women¹.

Satisfaction of the patient is crucial for maintaining and monitoring the quality of health care and can inform service development and delivery. Intra-partum satisfaction is a broad, multifaceted concept that includes experiences of the women during labour, birth and immediate postpartum period. Satisfaction in this context is often about giving birth in a manner that matches the needs of every woman².

The postpartum period is the time which reflects the approximate time required for uterine involution and return of most maternal body systems to a non-pregnant state. During this period physical recovery takes place as well as the women has to meet the needs of an infant. Evidences suggested that if these needs are unmet the stressors of the postpartum period can lead to anxiety, physical and mental illness³.

Women were dissatisfied with intra partum care. Mohammad K, Shaban I, Homer C, Creedy D2 conducted a study that support these findings. Data showed that the total mean satisfaction score with intra-partum care was 36.12(SD ± 8.88). They considered the score of ≥ 45 were positive towards increased satisfaction with intra-partum care. In this study only 17.8% (n=53) of the participants scored ≥ 45 and 82.2% (n=245) women scored lower suggesting dissatisfaction with the intra-partum care, 13% of women were satisfied with interpersonal care, in the area of information sharing and in making decision is 20.5% and whereas only 18.8% in physical birth environment.

A study also conducted on Chinese expectant parents by Zhang X and Lu H4. They tried to explore expectations regarding childbirth showed that the expectant parents had a high level expectations regarding childbirth in the area of care giving environment, spousal support, control and participation and medical support. Conversely their expectations towards labour pain and their own ability to cope with the pain were low. There were two predictors of expectant mothers' regarding childbirth expectations i.e. expectant fathers' expectations and partner's accompany as support person explaining 18.9% and 3.3% of the total variance respectively.

1.2. Need of the Study

Pregnancy and childbirth are important moments in the lives of pregnant women. Giving birth is the most special and memorable moment in a woman's life. Women always remember their labour experience and often find it very positive and enjoyable. But some women may have bad,

frightening childbirth experiences and they are quite anxious about this¹. So understanding women’s need during intra-partum and immediate postpartum period is one of the first steps to help and support women to achieve the most satisfying experience.

Dr. Abdel GR, and Dr. Berggren V5 conducted a study on parturient needs during labour of Egyptian women. They identified twenty-two needs from the women’s perspective. Among all of these needs the highest ranked needs for these women during labour were maintaining privacy through all procedures (86.5%), accessibility of nurses to demonstrate empathy (67.5%), availability to ventilate their feelings, fear and anxiety (57.5%), quick response on calling (67.5%), frequent monitoring (52.8%), accessibility of caring medical staff (47.2%) and short delivery (52.8%).

So, the investigator, by doing this research tries to help the women by identifying the needs and expectations during intra-partum and immediate postpartum period and helps to provide quality care to the women.

So, the investigator selected the study on does the health care provider fulfil the needs and expectations of women during intra-partum and immediate postpartum period in a selected Govt. hospital, West Bengal.

Purpose: The purpose of the study is to assess the care provided by the health care provider to fulfill the needs and expectations of women during intra-partum and immediate postpartum period.

Problem Statement: Does the health care provider fulfil the needs and expectations of women during intra-partum and immediate postpartum period in a selected Govt. hospital of West Bengal?

Figure 1: Conceptual framework based on Swanson’s Theory of caring and Roy’s Adaptation Model

1.3. Literature Related to Needs of Intra-Partum Women

Panda S, D'Sa J. and Rao AC6 conducted a descriptive study. The mean percentage distributions of scores under physical support needs were highest in needs (100%) as well as support (100%) for maintenance of hygiene and were lowest in needs (49.33%) in positioning and need for support (52.33%) in maintenance of hydration during labour.

A descriptive exploratory qualitative study was conducted by Iravani M, Zarean E, Janghorbani M, and Bahrami M. Study findings expressed that intervening to promote physiological needs can positively influenced on the women's sense of control and empowers during birthing. Some women were disappointed of restriction of eating and drinking during labour.

An analytic-cross sectional study was conducted by Dr Abdel GR and Dr Berggren V5 showed that twenty two need requirements emerged from women's perspective. 86.5% of women reported their needs for maintaining privacy through all procedure, 67.5% reported a need for qualified nurses offer help and demonstrate empathy.

A thorough systemic review was carried out by Iliadou M7 to identify practical points for supporting women in labour. Women during labour have a strong need for companionship, empathy and help. Continuous support appears to have a greater beneficial impact than intermittent support. Women's expectations of labour as a whole appear to be of more importance to their overall satisfaction with their labour experience than the perceived effectiveness of pain management.

1.4. Literature Related to Women's Expectations in Labour.

Zhang X and Lu H4 conducted a study on childbirth expectations. The total mean score of Childbirth Expectations Questionnaire was 4.14(SD=0.33) expectant mothers and 4.15(SD=0.30) for expectant fathers, revealed that couple's perceived a high level of childbirth expectations towards caring environment, spousal support, control and participation and medical support. Their expectations toward labour pain and their coping ability were relatively negative (M1=2.34, SD1=0.67; M2=2.46, SD2=0.65).

Pirdel M and Pirdel L8 conducted a descriptive-comparative study to compare women's expectations and experiences of childbirth. In the two groups, there was a negative significant relationship between the expectation and experience of childbirth in primiparas ($r = -0.62, p < 0.001$) and multiparas ($r = -0.69, p < 0.001$).

1.5. Literature Related to Needs and Expectation of Postpartum Women

Lindberg I, Ohrling K and Christensson K9 presented a study that showed that expectations of care in the maternity ward were 'the wish to have access to staff on the maternity ward' (99.3%), to have support during breastfeeding (90.6%), to have the family staying on the maternity ward (86.3%), and to have information about breastfeeding (85.4%) infant behaviour (82%) and childcare (82.7%).

2. Research Methodology

Figure 2: schematic presentation of descriptive research design

Figure 3: Schematic diagram of research methodology

Variables Under Study

Research variables

Needs of intra-partum and immediate postpartum women

Expectations of intra-partum and immediate postpartum women

Fulfilment of needs and expectations.

Demographic variables: Age, religion, gravida, education, family income, occupation of women, type of family.

Population

Population for the present study were all intra-partum and immediate postpartum women of West Bengal.

Sampling Technique

Non- probability purposive sampling technique was adopted for study .

Reliability of the Tool

Reliability of semi structured interview schedule for identification of the needs and expectations was computed by Kuder Richardson formula 20 method and reliability was 0.92. Reliability of 3 point Rating scale is established by Cronbach's alpha reliability method and the reliability was found 0.94.

Final Study

Final study conducted from 15.10.2018 to 24.11.2018. The investigator herself collected the data. After obtaining formal administrative permission from concerning authorities subjects were selected according to the inclusion criteria by using non-probability purposive sampling technique. Self-introduction was given to the subjects and established rapport with them. Explained the purpose of the study to the subjects and addressed the terms of confidentiality. Then informed consent for the study was obtained from the subjects. Separate code number was given to each subject. At first demographic data collected from the intra partum women. Then needs and expectations during intra-partum and immediate postpartum period were assessed by using semi structured interview schedule at observation room of Labour room from the women. After normal vaginal delivery the women were sent to postnatal ward. The investigator again collected data to assess the care provided by the health care provider to fulfil the needs and expectations from the women as they felt by introducing 3 point rating scale at postnatal ward at the time of discharge. After collecting the data investigator left the subjects with thanks. Total time taken for one interview was approximate 25 minutes at intra partum period and 20 minutes at immediate postpartum period.

Plan for Data Analysis

Plan for data analysis was planned to analyse by using descriptive and inferential statistics. Data were analysed by using percentage frequency and chi square. Bar, Pie diagram and table were used to represent the demographic characteristics of women. Intra partum and immediate post partum needs were represented through bar, cone and column diagram separately for every area. Fulfilment of needs and expectation of intra partum and immediate postpartum women were represented through cone diagram and pie diagram respectively. Chi-square and Correlation coefficient test were computed to find the association between selected demographic variables and fulfilment of needs. Unpaired 't' test was computed to find out the significant difference of mean score of primigravida and multigravida on needs fulfilment.

Analysis and Interpretation

Table 1: Sample Characteristics

Demographic Variables	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Age		
18-28 years	114	95
29-38 years	6	5
>39 years	0	0
Religion		
Hindu	50	41.66
Muslim	70	58.33
Others	0	0
Type of family		
Nuclear	70	58.33
Joint	50	41.66
Extended	0	0
Educational Status		
Illiterate	15	12.5
Primary	21	17.5
Madhyamik	57	47.5
H.S & above	27	22.5
Occupation		
Housewife	116	96.66
Businessmen	1	0.83
Service	3	2.5
Income of the family		
<Rs 2000/-	49	40.83
Rs 2001-5000/-	22	18.33
Rs 5000-10000/-	43	35.83
> Rs 10000/-	6	5
Gravida		
Primigravida	81	67.5
Multigravida	39	32.5

The data presented in the Table 1 depicts that most of women (95%) belongs to 18-28 years of age group, 58.33% women are Muslim & belong to nuclear family, maximum women were educated up to madhyamik (47.50%), most of (96.66%) women were housewife, Maximum family (40.83%) earned less than 2000 rupees and 67.5% women were primigravida.

Figure 4: Bar diagram showing percentage distribution of different informational needs regarding physical set up of intra-partum women.

Data presented in figure-4 depicts that majority (73%) of women asked information about physical set up of ward. Among them most of women (93.33%) wanted information about location of basin, bathroom, toilet and only 51.66% women wanted to know where was the doctors and nurses duty room.

Figure 5: Bar diagram showing percentage distribution of different informational needs related to labour & delivery of intra-partum women.

Data presented in fig-5 represents that most (89.04%) of the women wanted to know labour & delivery related information. But all women wanted information about foetal condition and most of the women wanted information about time of delivery (98.33%), who will conduct delivery (93.33%), what to do & not to do (96.67%), and majority of women wanted to know who will stand beside (75%) and whom to call in emergency (74.16%).

Figure 6: Bar diagram showing percentage distribution of different intra partum needs.

Data presented in figure 6 multiple bar diagram shows that all women (100%) have esteem need. Most of the women had informational needs regarding physical set up (73%), and labour & delivery related (89.04%), physiological need (92%), personal and psychological need (90%), social need (98.61%), safety need (95%) and majority of women had treatment need (62%).

Informational needs about Newborn care

Figure 7: Bar diagram showing different percent distribution of informational needs about newborn care of immediate postpartum women.

Data presented in figure-7 shows most (90.11%) of women wanted information about newborn care. Among them all women asked about baby care like breastfeeding technique, immunization, prevention of infection and danger signs of baby. Most of the women (95.83%) wanted to know the time of initiation of breast milk. Majority of women wanted to know about importance of colostrums (81.66%), how to maintain warmth of newborn (73.33%), signs of getting enough milk (80%).

Figure 8: Bar diagram depicting percentage distribution of different needs of women during immediate postpartum period.

Data presented in the figure-8 shows that all women had need for assistance, pain relieving and nutritional needs. Most of the women wanted information about newborn care (91.35%) and self care (95.62%) after delivery.

Summary of Intra-partum needs & expectations fulfillment

Figure 9: Cylinder diagram depicting percentage distribution of intra-partum needs and expectations according to fulfillment. Data presented in figure 22 depict that maximum (44.36%) intra-partum needs & expectations were partially fulfilled and only 19.32% needs were not fulfilled.

Summary of fulfillment of immediate postpartum needs and expectations

Figure 10: Column diagram depicting percentage distribution of postpartum needs and expectations according to fulfillment. Figure 23 presented data show that maximum needs & expectations (58%) during immediate postpartum period were partially fulfilled

Table 2: Association between educational status and intra partum needs, fulfillment of needs during intra partum period

Demographic variables	Intra partum needs		χ^2	Fishers exact	Fulfillment of intra partum needs		χ^2
	Present	Absent			Fulfilled	Not fulfilled	
Education	Informational needs						
	4	11	0.119	-	8	7	0.004
	20	85			57	48	
	Physiological needs						
	6	9	1.074	-	7	8	0.119
	57	48			54	51	
	Personal & psychological need						
Illiterate	9	6	0.019	-	2	13	5.257*
Literate	61	44			51	54	
	Social need				Esteem need		
	15	0	-	1.0	8	7	2.283
	100	5			35	70	
	Safety need						
	14	1	0.336	-	7	8	0.119
	88	17			54	51	
	Treatment need						
	4	11	0.0	-	8	7	0.875
	24	81			69	36	

With Yates correction χ^2 value at df (1) =3.84, $p < 0.05$, * significant

With Fisher's Exact Test, $p > 0.05$ at df (1)

The data presented in the table 2 reveal that there is no significant association between education and informational ($\chi^2=0.119$), physiological ($\chi^2=1.074$), personal & psychological ($\chi^2=0.019$), safety ($\chi^2=0.336$) and treatment need ($\chi^2=0.0$) and social need as the obtained p value 1.0 through Fisher's Exact test at df 1 at 0.05 level of significance.

However there is significant association found between education and fulfillment of personal & psychological as evident from χ^2 value 5.257 and no association found between education and fulfillment of informational ($\chi^2=0.004$), physiological ($\chi^2=0.119$), esteem ($\chi^2=2.283$), safety ($\chi^2=0.119$) and treatment need ($\chi^2=0.875$) at df 1 at 0.05 level of significance.

Table 3: Association between educational status and immediate postpartum needs, fulfillment of needs during immediate postpartum period.

N-120

Demographic variables	Immediate postpartum needs		χ^2	Fulfillment of immediate postpartum needs		χ^2
	Present	Absent		Fulfilled	Not fulfilled	
Education	Informational needs regarding newborn care					
	10	5	0.090	8	7	0.317
	74	31		64	41	
	Informational needs regarding self care					
Illiterate	13	2	0.008	8	7	3.883*
Literate	86	19		81	24	
	-			Assistance need		
				10	5	1.544
				52	53	
	-			Nutritional need		
				10	5	0.503
				79	26	

χ^2 value at df (1) = 3.84, $p < 0.05$, * significant

The data presented in the table 3 reveal that there is no significant association between education and informational need regarding newborn care ($\chi^2 = 0.090$) and self care ($\chi^2 = 0.008$) at df 1 at 0.05 level of significance.

However there is significant association between education and fulfillment of informational need regarding self care as evident from χ^2 value 3.883 and no association found between education and fulfillment of informational need regarding newborn care ($\chi^2 = 0.317$), assistance need ($\chi^2 = 1.544$) and nutritional need ($\chi^2 = 0.503$) at df 1 at 0.05 level of significance.

Table 4: Correlation coefficient 'r' showing relationship

N-120

Variables	Mean	r	Remarks
Gravida	1.325	-0.5483	Significant
Intra partum and immediate postpartum needs	52.933		

At df (118) 'r' value 0.174, $p < 0.05$ level of significance

Data presented in table 4 shows that there is moderate negative correlation between gravida and intra partum and immediate postpartum needs. It may be due to their experience. The relationship is statistically significant at 0.05 level of significance.

Table 5: Unpaired t-test

N-120

Gravida	Mean score of needs fulfillment	MD	SD _D	SE _{MD}	"t"-value
Multigravida	7.641	1.555	1.488	0.288	5.399*
Primigravida	6.086				

*Significant at df=118, $p < 0.05$, table value-1.9803

Data presented in table 5 depict that the t value is 5.399 at df 118. The obtained value (5.399) is higher than the table value (1.9803) at 0.05 level of significance. It means the mean difference is true difference between primigravida and multigravida not by chance. Therefore, interference can be drawn that there is significant difference of need fulfillment between multigravida and primigravida women.

3. Conclusion

Maximum of women's needs and expectations are partially fulfilled whereas needs and expectations are also not fulfilled and total fulfillment score is very low. So there is an urgent need to promote more focus on different types of needs and expectations of women during intra-partum and immediate postpartum period. Health care provider has the responsibility to provide quality care to pregnant women, which can be ensured by fulfilling the all needs and expectations of the woman during intra partum and immediate postpartum period. Findings from the study can be utilized to improve the quality care of women during hospitalization. Awareness of nursing personnel is needed regarding needs and expectations of women during intra-partum and immediate postpartum period. Findings of this study can be utilized to sensitize the nursing personnel from very beginning of their preparation period.

4. Recommendations

- A similar study can be conducted on large sample in different setting.
- A qualitative study can be conducted on fulfillment of needs and expectations.
- A comparative study can be conducted between primigravida and multigravida o this area.
- A study on effect of interventional package regarding needs, expectations and fulfillment on satisfaction level of clients can be conducted.

Acknowledgement

The research is the product of many person's contribution, extensive help, intensive knowledge and skills, who supported and encouraged the investigator throughout the study. These contributors helped the investigator as friends, philosophers and guides. It is her privilege to offer heartfelt thanks to all of them for their timely help to complete the task on time.

The investigator sincerely thanks the lord for his abundant grace, mental strength, blessings and unconditional love bestowed on investigator throughout the study.

The investigator expresses her deep sense of gratitude to her teacher and research guide Prof. Dr. Smritikana Mani, Principal of College of Nursing, Medical College & Hospital, Kolkata for her invaluable guidance and opinions which inspired investigator in successful completion of the study. Without her motivation and help, it would have been difficult for the investigator to complete the research study.

The investigator would like to express her profound sense of gratitude and heartfelt thanks to Ms Manasi Jana, Reader of College of Nursing, Medical College & Hospital, Kolkata for her valuable guidance, suggestions and opinions throughout the period of study.

The investigator extends sincere and heartiest thanks to all the faculty members of College of Nursing, Medical College & Hospital, Kolkata for their valuable suggestions and encouragement which led to the successful completion of the study.

The investigator extends special gratitude to all experts for their valuable contribution in validating, translating and reviewing the data collection tools.

The investigator is very much obliged to the Medical Superintendent cum Vice Principal of Medical College & Hospital, Kolkata for granting permission to conduct the study.

The investigator is indebted to the Head of the Department of Gynaecology and Obstetrics, Medical College & Hospital, Kolkata for granting permission and facilitating the accomplishment of the study. The investigator is thankful to Nursing Superintendent, Sister-In-Charge and all staff of labour room and postnatal ward of Medical College & Hospital, Kolkata.

The investigator gratefully mentions the efforts of Mr. Naresh Chandra Roy and Madhusudan Adhikary for language validation of data collection tool in English version and also in Bengali version.

The investigator's special thanks to the intra-partum and immediate postpartum women who have willingly participated and made the study possible.

An expression of gratitude goes to the librarians and other staff of the library of College of Nursing, Medical College & Hospital, Kolkata.

Profound gratitude is expressed to Dr. Sandip Mondal, Associate Professor of Calcutta University, for his patient endeavour in editing dissertation.

The investigator acknowledges the perseverance, understanding, and extension of encouragement and constant moral support of her family members during the entire period of the study. Word of acknowledgement would be incomplete if investigator does not express her sincere thanks to all friends and classmates.

The investigator extends her gratitude to all other members who directly and indirectly contributed their co-operation for the successful completion of research project.

Najnina Khatun
Investigator

Appendix A

A1: Letter seeking permission from Principal of C O N, Medical College & Hospital

To

The Principal,
College of Nursing
Medical College and Hospital
Kolkata -73

Subject: Requesting for permission for conducting a research study for fulfillment of M.Sc. Nursing course at College of Nursing, Medical College and Hospital

Respected Madam,

I beg to state that I, Najnina Khatun, M. Sc. Nursing student of College of Nursing, Medical College and Hospital, Kolkata. As per the requirement by The West Bengal University of Health Sciences, I have to complete a research dissertation for completion of M.Sc. Nursing course.

The topic selected for research study is “Does the health care provider fulfill the needs and expectations of women during intra-partum and immediate post-partum period in a selected Govt. Hospital of West Bengal”?

I will bear all the expenses of the research project on my own and will have informed consent and permission of the participants and concerned authorities before starting the study. Privacy, safety and confidentiality of all the study participants will be maintained strictly.

I shall be highly obliged if you kindly grant permission to conduct the proposed study.

Thanking you,
Yours sincerely

Najnina Khatun
M.Sc. Nursing student
College of Nursing,
Medical College & Hospital,
Kolkata
Date:

A2: Letter seeking permission from Institutional Ethical Committee

To,
The Chairperson
Institutional Ethical Committee
Medical College and Hospital
Kolkata-73

(Through proper channel)
Subject: Application for ethical clearance for proposed study

Sir/Madam,

I beg to state that I, Najnina Khatun, M. Sc. Nursing student of College of Nursing, Medical College and Hospital, Kolkata. As per the requirement by The West Bengal University of Health Sciences, I have to complete a research dissertation for completion of M.Sc. Nursing course.

The topic selected for research study is “Does the health care provider fulfill the needs and expectations of women during intra-partum and immediate post-partum period in a selected Govt. Hospital of West Bengal”? under the guidance of Prof. (Dr) Smritikana Mani, Principal of College of Nursing, Medical College and Hospital, Kolkata.

I will bear all the expenses of the research project on my own and will have informed consent and permission of the participants and concerned authorities before starting the study. Privacy, safety and confidentiality of all the study participants will be maintained strictly.

I shall be highly obliged if you kindly grant permission to conduct the proposed study.

Thanking you,
Yours sincerely

Najnina Khatun
M.Sc. Nursing student
College of Nursing,
Medical College & Hospital,
Kolkata
Date:

A3: Letter seeking permission from the Director of Health Services

Government of West Bengal
Office of the Principal
Govt. College of Nursing

Medical College & Hospital, Kolkata-700073, W.B

Phone No. 033-22551600 / 22123870 FAX – 033-22123806 E-mail: – medcon15kolkata@gmail.com

Memo No – HCN/CON/MCH/ 943

Date:- 25/9/18

To
The Director of Health Service
Swasthya Bhavan, GN-29, Sector –V, Salt Lake City,
West Bengal, Kolkata-700091

Subject: Seeking permission for conducting the pilot study from 4.10.18 to 11.10.18 and final research study from 15.10.18 to 17.11.18

Respected Sir/Madam,

I would like to introduce Ms. Najnina Khatun, final year M.Sc. Nursing student of this college to you. She has to conduct a research project and to submit to The West Bengal University of Health Sciences as a requirement of her course.

The topic selected for her research study is “Does the health care provider fulfill the needs and expectations of women during intra-partum and immediate post-partum period in a selected Govt. Hospital of West Bengal”?

The student is in need of your esteemed help and co-operation as she is interested in conducting pilot study from 4.10.18 to 11.10.18 and final study from 15.10.18 to 17.11.18 at Medical College and Hospital, Kolkata.

Therefore, I am requesting you to kindly give the permission and kindly extend necessary facilities to her work on the proposed study. Further information in this regard if any will be furnished by the student personally.

Thanking you.

Date:

Yours sincerely

Place:

Prof. Dr. Smritikana Mani

Principal, College of Nursing

Medical College Hospital, Kolkata

Principal
College of Nursing
Medical College and Hospital, Kolkata

A4: Letter seeking permission from the Joint Director of Health Services (Nursing)

Government of West Bengal
Office of the Principal
Govt. College of Nursing

Medical College & Hospital, Kolkata-700073, W.B

Phone No. 033-22551600 / 22123870 FAX – 033-22123806 E-mail: – medcon15kolkata@gmail.com

Memo No – HCN/CON/MCH/ 941

Date:- 25/9/18

To
The Joint Director of Health Services (Nursing)
Directorate of Health Service West Bengal
Swasthya Bhavan, GN-29, Sector –V, Salt Lake City,
West Bengal, Kolkata-700091

Subject: Seeking permission for conducting the pilot study from 4.10.18 to 11.10.18 and final research study from 15.10.18 to 17.11.18

Respected Sir/Madam,

I would like to introduce Ms. Najnina Khatun, final year M.Sc. Nursing student of this college to you. She has to conduct a research project and to submit to The West Bengal University of Health Sciences as a requirement of her course.

The topic selected for her research study is “Does the health care provider fulfill the needs and expectations of women during intra-partum and immediate post-partum period in a selected Govt. Hospital of West Bengal”?

The student is in need of your esteemed help and co-operation as she is interested in conducting pilot study from 4.10.18 to 11.10.18 and final study from 15.10.18 to 17.11.18 at Medical College and Hospital, Kolkata.

Therefore, I am requesting you to kindly give the permission and kindly extend necessary facilities to her work on the proposed study. Further information in this regard if any will be furnished by the student personally.

Thanking you.

Date:

Yours sincerely

Place:

Prof. Dr. Smritikana Mani

Principal, College of Nursing

Medical College Hospital, Kolkata

Principal
College of Nursing
Medical College and Hospital, Kolkata

A5: Letter seeking permission from MSVP of Medical College and Hospital

Government of West Bengal
Office of the Principal
Govt. College of Nursing
Medical College & Hospital, Kolkata-700073, W.B
Phone No. 033-22551600 / 22123870 FAX – 033-22123806
E-mail: – medcon15kolkata@gmail.com

Memo No-HCN/CON/MCH/ 1119 Date- 14.11.18
To
The Medical Superintendent cum Vice Principal
Medical College and Hospital
Kolkata

Subject: Seeking permission for conducting the Pilot study from 4.10.18 to 11.10.18 by M.Sc. Nursing Final Year student of College of Nursing, Medical College & Hospital, Kolkata-73.
Respected Sir/Madam,

I have the honour, to bring it to your kind information that according to the Government order vide Memo no. HNG/10P-3-2016/Pt-IV 893 dated 02/11/2018, Miss Najnina Khatun, M.Sc. Nursing, Final year student of College of Nursing, Medical College & Hospital, Kolkata, has been selected to undergo the study mentioned below for the Research project to be submitted to The West Bengal University of Health Sciences for partial fulfillment of university requirements of Master of Science degree in Nursing.

Problem statement for Dissertation: “Does the health care provider fulfill the needs and expectations of women during intra-partum and post-partum period in a selected govt. hospital of West Bengal”?

In this connection, she is in need of your necessary permission on all sorts of cooperation in conduction of her pilot study at the following settings of your institution (if needed the data collection period may be extended).

Pilot Study: Medical College and Hospital, Kolkata.
Therefore, I would like to solicit your benign approval with all respective concern as to facilitate her to conduct the study at your early convenience please.
Thanking you

Yours sincerely

Date: 14.11.2018

Place: Kolkata.

Prof. Dr Smritikana Mani
Principal, College of Nursing
Medical College and Hospital, Kolkata-73

Memo no- HCN/CON/MCH/

Copy forwarded to:

4. The HOD, Gynecology & Obstetrics Department, MCH, Kol-73.
5. The Nursing Superintendent, MCH, Kol-73.
6. The Sister in charge, Labour Room, MCH, Kol-73.

Principal
College of Nursing
Medical College and Hospital, Kolkata

(Prof. Dr. Smritikana Mani)
Principal
College of Nursing
Medical College & Hospital, Kol-73

Received with thanks
but not verified
14.11.18
Signature
M.C.H., Kol.

A6: Letter seeking permission from MSVP of Medical College and Hospital

Government of West Bengal
Office of the Principal
Govt. College of Nursing
Medical College & Hospital, Kolkata-700073, W.B
Phone No. 033-22551600 / 22123870 FAX – 033-22123806
E-mail: – medcon15kolkata@gmail.com

Memo No-HCN/CON/MCH/ 1120

Date- 14.11.18

To
The Medical Superintendent cum Vice Principal
Medical College and Hospital
Kolkata

Subject: Seeking permission for conducting the Final study 15.10.18 to 17.11.18 by M.Sc. Nursing Final Year student of College of Nursing, Medical College & Hospital, Kolkata-73.

Respected Sir/Madam,

I have the honour, to bring it to your kind information that according to the Government order vide Memo no. HNG/10P-3-2016/Pt-IV 893 dated 02/11/2018, Miss Najnina Khatun, M.Sc. Nursing, Final year student of College of Nursing, Medical College & Hospital, Kolkata, has been selected to undergo the study mentioned below for the Research project to be submitted to The West Bengal University of Health Sciences for partial fulfillment of university requirements of Master of Science degree in Nursing.

Problem statement for Dissertation: “Does the health care provider fulfill the needs and expectations of women during intra-partum and post-partum period in a selected govt. hospital of West Bengal”?

In this connection, she is in need of your necessary permission on all sorts of cooperation in conduction of her final study at the following settings of your institution (if needed the data collection period may be extended).

Final Study: Medical College and Hospital, Kolkata.

Therefore, I would like to solicit your benign approval with all respective concern as to facilitate her to conduct the study at your early convenience please.

Thanking you

Yours sincerely

Date: 14.11.18

Place: Kolkata.

Prof. Dr Smritikanta Mani
Principal, College of Nursing
Medical College and Hospital, Kolkata-73

Memo no- HCN/CON/MCH/

Copy forwarded to:

1. The HOD, Gynecology & Obstetrics Department, MCH, Kol-73.
2. The Nursing Superintendent, MCH, Kol-73.
3. The Sister in charge, Labour Room, MCH, Kol-73.

Received with thanks
but not verified

Sh.
14.11.18

Signature
M.C.H., Kol.

(Prof. Dr. Smritikanta Mani)
Principal,
College of Nursing
Medical College & Hospital, Kolkata-73

Appendix B

B1: Letter granting permission from Principal of C O N, Medical College & Hospital

To
The Principal
College of Nursing
Medical College & Hospital
Kolkata-700073

(Through proper channel)

Sub: Requesting permission to conduct the research study.

Respected Madam,

With due respect & humble submission I, Najnina Khatun, M.Sc. Nursing student of College of Nursing, Medical College & Hospital, Kolkata beg to state that I have to conduct a research project for the partial fulfilment of the University's requirement for the award of M.Sc. degree in nursing. The study will be conducted at Medical College and Hospital, Kolkata.

The statement of the problem is----.

“Does the health care provider fulfill the needs and expectations of women during intra-partum and immediate postpartum period in a selected Govt. hospital of West Bengal?”

In this matter I would like to request you to grant permission to conduct the study in the pre-mentioned location.

Thanking you.

Dated:

Yours faithfully,

Najnina Khatun

Najnina Khatun

M.Sc. Nursing Student

College of Nursing

Medical College and Hospital

Kolkata

Principal
9.4.2018
Principal
College of Nursing
Medical College and Hospital, Kolkata

B2: Letter granting permission from Institutional Ethical Committee

INSTITUTIONAL ETHICS COMMITTEE
(Reg. No. – ECR/287/Inst/WB/2013)
MEDICAL COLLEGE, KOLKATA
88, COLLEGE STREET, KOLKATA 700073, WEST BENGAL, INDIA

Chairperson

Prof. S. K. Maitra

Member Secretary

Prof. A.K.Bhadra

Members

Prof. Aniruddha Sengupta
Prof. Debabrata Bandyopadhyay
Prof. Tapan Mukhopadhyay
Prof. Manideepa Sengupta
Prof. Suhrita Pal
Dr. Rudrajit Paul
Dr. NilayKanti Das
Mr. Hironlal Majumdar
Ms. Sebanti Bhattacharya
Ms. Suhrita Saha
Ms. Rehana Khatun
Mr. Ashok Kar

Ref No MC/KOL/IEC/ NON-SPON/71/05-2018

Dated: 12.05.2018

To,
Ms. Najnina Khatun,
M.Sc Nursing 1st year student,
College of Nursing,
Medical College & Hospital, Kolkata

Sub.: IEC- MCH Decision of the review of study ref No. nil , dated nil .

Study Title: Problem Statement:

Does the health care provider fulfill the needs and expectation of women during intra-partum and immediate postpartum period in a selected Govt. Hospital of West Bengal?

Dear Student,

In its meeting held on 12th May, 2018, the members of the IEC, Medical College, Kolkata, the above related documents were examined, reviewed and discussed your proposal to conduct the above mentioned study.

The following members of the committee were present (ticked against their names):

✓ **Chairperson:** Prof. Susanta Kr. Maitra, Pharmacologist

✓ **Member Secretary:** Prof. Ashok Kumar Bhadra, Principal, MCH

Members

✓ Prof. Aniruddha Sengupta (Clinician)
✓ Prof. Debabrata Bandyopadhyay (Clinician)
✓ Prof. Tapan Mukhopadhyay (Basic Scientist)
✓ Prof. Manideepa Sengupta (Basic Scientist)
✓ Prof. Suhrita Pal (Pharmacologist)
✓ Dr. Rudrajit Paul (Clinician)
✓ Dr. NilayKanti Das (Clinician)
✓ Mr. Hironlal Majumdar (Legal Expert)
✓ Ms. Sebanti Bhattacharya (Philosopher)
Ms. Suhrita Saha (Sociologist)
Ms. Rehana Khatun (Medically Lay person)
✓ Mr. Ashok Kar (Medically Lay person)

B2

INSTITUTIONAL ETHICS COMMITTEE
(Reg. No. – ECR/287/Inst/WB/2013)
MEDICAL COLLEGE, KOLKATA
88, COLLEGE STREET, KOLKATA 700073, WEST BENGAL, INDIA

Study Title: : Problem Study: Does the health care provider fulfill the needs and expectation of women during intra-partum and immediate postpartum period in a selected Govt. Hospital of West Bengal?

The committee has decided to:

- Approve the study protocol in the present form.
- Conditionally approve the study protocol subject to
-
-
- Reject the proposal for the following reasons
-
-

You are required to:

- i) Inform the committee about the progress of the study and compliance of ethical guidelines.
- ii) Notify the committee regarding any serious adverse events occurring in the course of the study.
- iii) Inform and seek approval of the committee about any changes in the protocol prior to their implementation.
- iv) Submit the final report to the committee in every case.

This Ethics committee is working in accordance with the ICH-GCP, Schedule Y and ICMR guidelines and other applicable regulations.

Yours truly,

Chairperson / Member Secretary
IEC
Medical College, Kolkata

Member Secretary
Institutional Ethics Committee
Medical College, Kolkata

Appendix C

C1: Letter seeking Expert’s opinion for content validity

To

.....
.....

Subject: Requesting letter for seeking expert’s opinion & suggestion for content validation of data collection tool.

Respected Sir/Madam

I Najnina Khatun, M.Sc. Nursing student, in order to meet the course requirement, going to conduct a dissertation work.

Topic: “Does the health care provider fulfill the needs and expectations of women during intra-partum and immediate post-partum period in a selected Govt. Hospital of West Bengal”?

Objectives

- 1) To assess the needs of the women during intra-partum and immediate postpartum period.
- 2) To assess the expectations of the women during intra-partum and immediate postpartum period.
- 3) To assess the care provided by the health care provider to fulfill the needs and expectations of women during intra-partum and immediate postpartum period

For above purpose I have prepared

- A structured questionnaire for demographic variables.
- Semi structured questionnaire to identify needs and expectations.
- 3 point rating scale to assess fulfillment of needs and expectations.

I am requesting you to kindly go through the content of the tool and give your expert opinion and suggestion about the appropriateness of the item which needs to be modified and deleted by using evaluation checklist. I would like to go take your permission for keeping your name in the expert list of my dissertation.

This is also my request that, kindly sign the certificate of validation that is enclosed with tool. I will remain grateful if you kindly provide me your expert judgment by checking my tool.

Thanking you.

Date:

Yours sincerely
Najnina Khatun
M.Sc. Nursing student
College of Nursing
Medical College & Hospital
Kolkata

C2: Certificate for tool validation

To Whom It May Concern

This is to certify that the tool which was developed by Ms. Najnina Khatun, student of M.Sc. Nursing, College of Nursing, Medical College & Hospital, Kolkata-73 on research topic “Does the health care provider fulfill the needs and expectations of women during intra-partum and immediate post-partum period in a selected Govt. Hospital of West Bengal ?” has been validated by me and the comments are noted.

Signature:

Name:

Designation:

Date:

Seal:

D1: Certificate for editing the research study

Editing certificate for research study

To whom it may concern

This is to certify that Ms. Najnina Khatun, final year M.Sc. Nursing student (2017-2019), College of Nursing, Medical College & Hospital, Kolkata-73 has made the necessary editorial changes successfully. Her dissertation paper is titled **“Does the health care provider fulfil the needs and expectations of women during intra-partum and immediate post-partum period in a selected Govt. Hospital of West Bengal ?”**

I wish her success in life.

Date: 21.05.19

Signature

Place: Kolkata

DESIRAJ MONDAL
Associate Professor
Dept of English
University of Calcutta

Appendix E

E1: Informed Consent Form in English

I have been properly explained by the researcher the purpose and method of this research (Does the health care provider fulfill the needs and expectations of women during intra-partum and immediate postpartum period in a selected Govt. hospital of West Bengal?). My participation in this study is purely voluntary and I can withdraw from the study whenever I wish. I have also understood that the researcher can take any decision regarding my participation in the study. I will not be given any incentive for participating in this study. After agreeing to participate in this study I give my full consent for participation and shall fully cooperate with the researcher for achievement of the objectives provided confidentiality is maintained.

NAME OF THE PARTICIPANT :
SIGNATURE/LTI :
DATE :
NAME OF THE WITNESS :
SIGNATURE :
DATE :
NAME OF RESEARCHER :
SIGNATURE :
PHONE NO :
DATE :

Appendix F

Data collection tool

F1: Semi structure Interview Schedule

Part I

Purpose- To collect demographic data from intra partum women.

Instruction – The investigator will ask questions and put tick () mark against the answer given by the women.

Code no:

- 1) Age:.....
 - i. 18 years to 28 years ()
 - ii. 29 years to 39 years ()
 - iii. >39 years ()
- 2) Religion :.....
 - i. Hindu ()
 - ii. Muslim ()
 - iii. Christian or others ()
- 3) Type of family :.....
 - i. Nuclear family ()
 - ii. Joint family ()
 - iii. Extended family ()
- 4) Educational qualification:.....
 - i. Illiterate ()
 - ii. Primary ()
 - iii. Madhyamik
 - iv. Higher secondary and above ()
- 5) Occupation :.....
 - i. Homemaker ()
 - ii. Business ()
 - iii. Service ()
- 6) Monthly income:.....
 - i. < Rs 2000 per month ()
 - ii. Rs 2001 to 5000/month ()
 - iii. Rs 5001 to 10000 per month ()
 - iv. > Rs 10000 per month ()
- 7) Gravida :
 - i. Primi-gravida ()
 - ii. Multi-gravida ()

F 2 Semi structured interview schedule

Purpose – To assess the needs of the women during intra-partum and immediate postpartum period.

Instruction – The investigator will ask the questions and write the answers given by the women in intra-partum & immediate post-partum period.

Code no:

Part II (A) Intra-partum period

Informational needs

Q.1. What information do you need regarding the ward environment (like location of basin, toilet and bathroom, Doctors and nurses station etc)?

Q.2 What information do you need regarding your labour and delivery process? (Foetal condition, Time of delivery, Plan of delivery, Who will stand besides you, Who will conduct delivery, Whom to call in emergency, What to do & not to do).

Physiological needs

Q.3. What do you want to get services regarding your physiological needs? (information about whom to call in nausea, vomiting or headache occur, information whom to call if foetal movement is less, to check blood pressure, pulse, to check foetal heart rate, Information about type of diet to be taken during, before, after delivery, help to take light diet, help to take drinking water).

Personal and Psychological needs

Q.4. What services do you want to get to maintain your personal hygiene? (Help to clean the body or to take bath, help to change the clothing)

Q.5. What do you want to maintain your physical comfort in this ward? (comfortable environment in terms of light, temperature and cleanliness, Clean bed linen).

Q.6. What kind of behaviour do you want to get from health care provider? (Behave kindly with you, verbal encouragement, Response in calling).

Social needs

Q.7. What are your needs to maintain communication regarding delivery from health care provider? (Allowing support person like one family member to stay with you, Communication of the health care provider with you, Communication of the health care provider with family member).

Esteems needs

Q.8. What are your needs regarding respectful maternity care like maintain privacy during check up or delivery like use of curtain, screen, no physical harm, consent before doing any procedure, equal treatment indiscriminating caste, creed, rich or poor, respect like calling by “name” or by “you”, freedom in care like involvement in decision making, allowing comfortable position for delivery, to get timely care.

Security needs

Q.9. What are your needs regarding security? (Explanation about every procedure, Removing fear of childbirth process, Removing -fear of losing baby).

Treatment needs

Q.10. What do you want to get treatment or medical services? (Pain relieving measures to relieve pain, Prevention of unnecessary intervention like frequently use of urinary catheter and vaginal examination.)

Part II (B)

Immediate postpartum period

Informational needs

Regarding newborn care

1. What information do you need regarding breast feeding (when to initiate breast feeding, either colostrums is given or not, breastfeeding technique)?
2. What information do you need to know from health care provider to maintain warmth of newborn (type of baby's clothing, time of bathing)?
3. What information do you need to know from health care provider regarding baby's immunizations like when or where to give immunization?
4. What information do you need to know from health care provider to prevent infection?
5. What information do you need to know from health care provider to know the signs of baby is getting enough milk?
6. What information do you need to know from health care provider about the danger signs of baby?

Regarding self care

7. What information do you want to know regarding postnatal diet?
8. What information do you want to know to take perineal care like dressing, pad changing ?
9. What information do you want to know about the danger signs of postnatal mother?

Assistance needs

10. What services do you want from health care provider to take care of self (assistance to change clothing, sanitary napkin, cleaning extremities, in ambulation) and newborn care (supporting to hold baby during breastfeeding)?

Pain relieving needs

11. What do you need to relieve pain at perineal area?

Nutritional needs

12. What do you want to get services regarding nutrition like providing food and water?

Other need

13. What other information or services do you want from health care provider during intrapartum or immediate postpartum period?

F 3: 3 point Rating Scale

Purpose: To assess the care provided by the health care provider to fulfil the expectations of women during intra-partum and immediate post-partum period.

Instruction: During intra-partum and post partum period women have some expectations from health care provider to fulfil their needs. I would like to assess the care to fulfil the expectations of women during intra-partum and immediate post partum period. I will ask some statement and you will give answer according to your expectations are fulfilled by “totally fulfilled” “partially fulfilled” or “not fulfilled”.

Code no:

Intra-partum period (Part III A)

Sl no	Area & Sub area	Expectations (fulfilment of needs) of women during intra-partum period	Totally fulfilled	Partially fulfilled	Not fulfilled
1	Informational need a. Hospital Environment b. Labour & Delivery	i. Health care provider gave full information about location of basin, toilet and bathroom after admission. ii. Health care provider shown you the nurses and Doctors station. i. Health care provider gave information about who will stand besides you during delivery. ii. Who will conduct the delivery either doctor or nursing staff was informed by health care provider. iii. Information about foetal condition was given by health care provider. iv. Health care provider informed you about the time of labour. v. Health care provider informed you about the plan of delivery like normal or caesarean section. vi. Health care provider informed you whom to call if any problem occur. vii. Health care provider gave information about do's and don'ts during labour like ambulation till membrane is intact, don't give bearing down pain in first stage, don't take heavy food before delivery			

2	Physiological needs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> i. Health care provider informed you whom to call in nausea, vomiting or headache. ii. Health care provider informed whom to call if there is less foetal movement. iii. Health care provider checked your pulse and blood pressure four hourly. iv. Health care provider checked foetal heart rate every 30 minutes interval. v. Health care provider gave information about diet during, before and after delivery. vi. Health care provider helped to take light diet like biscuit, flattened rice. vii. Health care provider helped to take drinking water. 			
3	Personal and psychological need	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> i. Health care provider assisted to take bath or clean the body. ii. Health care provider helped you to change your clothing. iii. Health care provider maintained comfortable physical environment in terms of light, and temperature and cleanliness. iv. Health care provider provided clean bed linens. v. Health care provider shown kind behaviour. vi. Health care provider gave verbal encouragement during labour. vii. Health care provide gave attention when you need like give response when you call. 			
4	Social needs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> i. Health care provider allowed support person to stay with you. ii. Health care provider communicated clearly with you regarding delivery. iii. Health care provider communicated clearly with family member about the labour progress. 			

5.	Esteem needs Respectful maternity care	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> i. Health care provider maintained privacy by using curtain, screen throughout labour. ii. No physical harm was inflicted by health care provider during delivery. iii. Health care provider took consent before any procedure. iv. Health care provider treated equally indiscriminating caste, creed, rich or poor. v. Health care provider allowed taking any decision or comfortable position during delivery. vi. Health care provider took care timely. vii. Health care provider took care with respect (calling by name, you). 			
6.	Safety needs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> i. Health care provider gave explanation before procedure. ii. Health care provider removed fear of losing baby. iii. Health care provider removed fear of child birth process. 			
7.	Treatment needs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> i. Health care provider gave medication to relief pain. ii. Health care provider prevented unnecessary intervention like frequently catheterization, per vaginal examination. 			

Immediate post-partum period (Part III B)

Sl no	Area & sub area	Expectation (fulfilment of needs) of women during immediate post-partum period	Totally fulfilled	Partially fulfilled	Not fulfilled
1	Informational needs a. Newborn care	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> i. Health care provider informed and helped to initiate of breast feeding within 30minutes. ii. Health care provider explained the importance of colostrums, either it is given to baby or not. iii. Health care provider demonstrated breastfeeding technique. 			

	<p>b. Self-care after delivery</p>	<p>iv. Health care provider instructed to keep the baby warm by the use of cotton clean cloth, covering whole body of baby including head & extremities.</p> <p>v. Health care provider explained about immunization like where and when to give vaccine.</p> <p>vi. Health care provider explained about how to prevent infection like proper hand washing before holding the baby, nothing will be applied on umbilical cord, holding baby bath until umbilical cord fallen off.</p> <p>vii. Health care provider made you understand the signs of baby is getting enough milk like passing of urine after feeding, 6-8 time passing of stool per day, quite sleep after feeding.</p> <p>viii. Health care provider gave information about the danger signs of baby such as refusal to feed, hypothermia, convulsion.</p> <p>i. Health care provider gave information about postnatal diet like take extra amount of food, green leafy vegetables, enough water.</p> <p>ii. Health care provider explained how to take care of the perineum such as cleaning of perineum after passing urine & stool, applying ointment on suture, using sanitary pad.</p> <p>iii. Health care provider instructed to check the amount & colour of lochia.</p>			
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		iv. Health care provider gave information about the danger signs such as excessive bleeding; pad is saturated within 1 hour, blurring vision, headache, and convulsion.			
2	Supporting needs	i. Health care provider assisted to change sanitary napkin and clothing immediately after delivery. ii. Health care provider helped to clean perineum immediately after delivery. iii. Health care provider helped to clean the extremities immediately after delivery. iv. Health care provider gave assistance in ambulation immediately after delivery. v. Health care provider gave support to hold the baby during breastfeeding.			
3	Need for pain relief	i. Health care provider gave pain relieving medication.			
4	Nutritional need	i. Health care provider helped to take food. ii. Health care provider provided enough drinking water.			

F 4: 3 point Rating Scale (Fulfilment of needs and expectation)

Sl no.	Expectations (fulfilment of needs)	Code
1	Totally fulfilled	T
2	Partially fulfilled	P
3	Not fulfilled	N

G 1: Part II A (Semi Structured Interview Schedule)

Code No	Informational needs									Physiological needs						Personal & Psychological needs					
	Location of basin bathroom and Location of doctors & nurses station	Foetal condition	Time of delivery	Plan of delivery	Who will stand besides her	Delivery conducted by whom	Whom to call in emergency	Do's & don'ts during labour	Whom to call in nausea vomiting	whom to call in less foetal movement	Need to check pulse & blood	Need to check foetal heart rate	Need to know nature of diet	Need to help to take diet	Need to help to take drinking water	Need help to take bath	Need help to change clothing	Comfortable environment	Clean bed linen	Kind behaviour	Response in calling
1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	1
2	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1
3	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1
4	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
5	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1
6	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	1
7	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
8	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	0	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	1
9	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
10	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1
11	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	1
12	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	1
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14	1	0	1	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	1
15	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	1
16	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	1	1
17	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	0
18	1	0	1	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1
19	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
20	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0
21	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
22	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
23	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
24	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1

25	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
26	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
27	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
28	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
29	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0
30	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	0
31	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1
32	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1
33	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
34	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	0
35	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
36	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
37	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
38	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
39	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
40	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
41	1	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
42	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
43	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
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